

Level of Application of Assisted Reproductive Technologies in Cattle Production in Sokoto Metropolis North-Western Nigeria: A Retrospective Study.

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The need to attain full food security and improve the economy of the country is a challenge being addressed by all stakeholders. The livestock subsector is one that need improvement to meet or reduce the effect of these challenges. One way of addressing the bane in livestock production is the application of assisted reproductive technologies (ART's) such as estrus synchronization, super ovulation, embryo recovery and transfer. The study was carried out in Sokoto metropolis to document retrospectively, the level of application of reproductive technologies in farms into cattle production. Five cattle farms identified within the study area were administered questionnaire. Estrus synchronization and artificial insemination were the only reproductive technologies practiced by the farmers in the study area. Most reason attributed to the low application of reproductive technologies are high cost, failures and lack of enlightenment. Other technologies like embryo transfer, *invitro* fertilization (IVF) and cloning were not known by farmers within the study area or there was paucity of their knowledge as assisted reproductive procedures in livestock industry. Enlightenment about reproductive technologies, government interventions and proper record keeping, among others are recommended to increase the level of application of reproductive technology in cattle within Sokoto metropolis so as to optimize productivity within the livestock industry.

Keywords: estrus, reproductive, technologies, cattle

INTRODUCTION

Reproductive technologies are improved methods which enhance and optimize reproduction, productivity in terms of byproducts from animals, conservation of animal breeds and disease reduction or eradication.

Reproductive technologies encompasses all current and anticipated uses of technology in human and animal reproduction, including assisted reproductive technology, contraception and others (Mapletoft & Hasler, 2005).

Various techniques have been developed and refined to obtain a large number of offspring from

genetically superior animals or obtain offspring from infertile (or sub fertile) animals (Naqvi *et al.*, 2001; Blackburn, 2004). Reproductive technologies include artificial insemination (AI), embryo transfer (ET) at times referred to as multiple ovulation and embryo transfer (MOET), estrus synchronization (ES), intra cytoplasmic sperm-injection (ICSI), invitro embryo production (IVP), oocyte/embryo cryopreservation and vitrification, zygote intra fallopian transfer (ZIFT), gamete intra fallopian transfer (GIFT), cloning.

For this study, the focus shall be on the application of AI, ES and ET. AI and ES being the common reproductive technologies practiced in majority of developing countries such as Nigeria due to the deficit in technological infrastructure. The level of application of

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these technologies which maximizes the potential and profitability of the livestock industry is of paramount importance in this study as this will help to be better equipped for the evolving world of livestock farming. Thus, after the establishment of the level of application of these technologies, an empirical fact which will tend to inform on the optimization of the livestock industry with recourse to reproduction ensues. Also to be revealed are reasons responsible for decline in the application of these technologies if that be the case as may be espoused by the study. Reproductive technologies in cattle concurrent with the success or otherwise of its application as it relates to increase profitability and productivity of the livestock industry with decrease in the development of diseases are what this study seeks to address.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Five cattle farms located within Sokoto metropolis were identified for the study. The farms were visited for familiarization at first and later visited for administration of questionnaire and documentation. The identified farms were named A, B, C, D and E for the purpose of this study:

A questionnaire was designed and administered to determine response to the following parameters:

- Farm name
- Farm Address
- System of Management
- Number of cattle on the Farm
- Number of bulls on the Farm
- Number of cows on the Farm
- Breeds of cattle on the Farm
- Name of breed(s) on the Farm
- Production system
- Mode of Reproduction
- Type of reproductive technology (RT) employed
- Duration of use of such Reproductive Technology
- Year in review together with the type of RT employed, number of animals involved, number of successful case(s), number of calves produced.
- Capacity of milk production (liters/day) from cows given birth to through RT.
- Cost/liter of milk produced.
- Total cost incurred with the use of RT on the Farm.
- Weight(s) of beef cattle given birth to through RT.
- Cost/beef cattle produced through RT.
- Capacity of milk production (liters/day) from imported foreign/pure exotic and local breed of cattle on the farm.
- Weight (kg) of beef cattle that are either imported foreign/pure exotic and local breed of cattle on the farm.

- Means of acquisition of foreign breed(s) of cattle.
- Cost of means of importation.
- Reasons for not opting for RT.
- Advice to increase the level of application of RT within Sokoto metropolis.

RESULTS

Farm A carried out 'Natural estrus and AI' in 2012 and 2013 with the involvement of 300 cattle (cows) and 30 calves which included 19 females and 11 males were produced amounting to a success rate of 10%.

Farm D carried out 'Estrus synchronization and Artificial insemination' in 2012 and 2017 with the involvement of 15 cows in 2012 and 24 cows in 2017 with no success recorded in 2012 and 2 calves (2 males) produced in 2017 amounting to a success rate of 5%.

Table 1: Number of successful cases with the use of reproductive technology on the farms that employed it.

Figure 1. Number of males and females produced from the use of reproductive technology on the farms.

DISCUSSION

The level of application of reproductive technologies on cattle such as artificial insemination (AI), estrus synchronization (ES), which are the commonest within Sokoto metropolis as shown by the result of this study is

low, below average. Various assisted reproductive techniques have been developed and refined to obtain a large number of offspring from genetically superior animals or obtain offspring from infertile (or subfertile) animals (Widayati, 2012) in addition to disease control (Mapletoft, 2013), this boost production as genetically superior animals in livestock products production such as milk and muscle mass can be easily and cost effectively obtained from the use of reproductive technologies. Three out of the five farms visited practice intensive system of management while the other two practice semi-intensive system of management, both intensive and semi-intensive system of management allow for monitoring of cattle which is essential for estrus synchronization and artificial insemination. The ratio of bulls to cows on the farms visited is 1:17 for farm A, 1:12 for farm B, 1:1 for farm C, 1:3 for farm D while the ratio for farm E wasn't ascertained. All the farms visited have foreign, local and cross-bred cattle. The farms visited practice dairy production system which buttresses the point for increase in the number of females compared to the number of males for majority of the farms visited.

Only 2 of the 5 farms identified and visited attempted the use of reproductive technologies. The reproductive technologies employed on these farms are artificial insemination and estrus synchronization. A success rate of 10% and 5% was recorded for farms that attempted the use of artificial insemination. Also of note is an instance when there was no success rate at all with the use of artificial insemination on one of the farms. The cost incurred with the use of estrus synchronization and artificial insemination is estimated at #15000 per cow and #5000 per day for other provisions such as feeding and accommodation as inseminators are not residents of Sokoto metropolis.

Foreign breeds of cattle are reported to produce the highest quantity of milk followed by cross-bred (cross between foreign and local) and then local breeds of cattle by all but one of the farms visited. Cost per liter of milk as reported by the farms visited is averaged at #250 per liter. Two of the farms engage in direct importation of foreign breeds, two (2) engage in local purchase of foreign breeds, while only 1 farm engage in both local purchase and importation of foreign breeds. Total number of foreign breeds of cattle obtained through direct importation are 29 across the farms visited while those obtained through local purchase are 67.

CONCLUSION

From the result obtained from the farms visited, it is evident that the level of application of reproductive technologies on cattle within Sokoto metropolis is low, below average. The commonest of these technologies which are artificial insemination and estrus

synchronization are underutilized talk more of complex and sophisticated reproductive technologies such as embryo transfer, intra cytoplasmic sperm-injection (ICSI), invitro embryo production (IVP), oocyte/embryo cryopreservation and vitrification, zygote intra fallopian transfer (ZIFT), gamete intra fallopian transfer (GIFT). The result also shows that foreign breeds of lactating cows produces more milk than local breeds of lactating cows and cross-bred (foreign and local breeds) produces more milk than the local breeds.

The cost of acquiring foreign breeds to cross with local breeds to generate cross-breeds is high, therefore with the application of reproductive technologies such as artificial insemination which is at a cost very low compared to importation or local purchase of foreign breeds for the same purpose should be considered as many more cross-breeds can be generated at a relatively low sum total and less risk. The AI technology maximizes the use of outstanding males, dissemination of superior genetic material, improve the rate and efficiency of genetic selection on the male side, introduction of new genetic material by import of semen rather than live animals and thus, reducing the international transport costs, enabling the use of frozen semen even after the donor is dead and reduces the risk of spreading sexually transmitted diseases (Foote, 2002).

Sufficient funds could be saved with the use of reproductive technologies such as AI as the cost of acquisition of a foreign breed is multiple times the cost of AI which at the end will give similar results or an even better result with AI so far the technology is perfected. The use of estrus synchronization as well aids in positioning large number of cows at similar reproductive stage such that large number of cows will lactate at a similar time as well synchronizing farm activities in an orderly manner and aiding strategic business planning. The reasons for the low level of application of reproductive technologies may not be unconnected with decrease success rate obtained from previous use.

RECOMMENDATION

- Livestock farmers and stakeholders within the livestock industry should be enlightened about reproductive technologies and it's benefits by veterinarians and professionals in such field alike.
- Farm owners or personnel in charge should be encouraged and admonished to keep proper records.
- Government at all levels should help in provisions of facility and funds for the use of reproductive technologies, even if it is at subsidized rate for easy access.
- Veterinary doctors and professionals alike in such field should keep up to date with new discoveries related to livestock development and be trained and retrained to
- perfect the skills of reproductive technologies for increase in the success rate of its use.

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